

Role of Digitalization in Improving the Logistics Distribution Performance

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Abstract: Fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) touch every individual's life in one way; these goods are characterized by thin margins and require seamless distribution. The development and capacity of completed wares from the place of assembling to the client is alluded to as physical distribution. The challenge for management is to ensure improved logistics distribution. With the advent of digital technology, many tools are designed to capture the data and gauge the inefficiencies in distribution. The logistics performance of fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) is highly reliant on transportation and warehouse performance and this can be improved through digitalization. This paper studies the distribution of fast-moving consumer goods and tries to identify the inefficiencies in transportation and warehousing operations. The factors leading to inefficiencies in transportation and warehouse performance are identified through a literature review. Five elements that have a direct impact on transport performance have been identified. Similarly, six elements were identified that directly impact the warehouse's performance. The objective is to evaluate the effect of digitalization on coordinated operations dispersion execution. The data are collected through structured questionnaires from 256 managers and executives employed in the FMCG sector. The data are analyzed through Structural equation modeling (SEM) with AMOS. The conceptual model is formulated, and hypotheses are tested based on the model.

Keywords: Distribution Performance, Transportation, Warehousing, Digitalization, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)

1. Introduction

Quick customer merchandise (FMCG), is the fourth-biggest area in India that incorporates family and individual consideration items representing half of complete FMCG deals (Husain, 2021). The sector's growth is backed by the drivers that include increased awareness, greater access, and changing consumer preferences (Naik and Sudina, 2017). Due to higher volumes and a vast network, the FMCG sector has the greatest material and logistics costs. Poor resource utilization and infrastructural constraints are attributed to the higher logistical costs (Napoli et al., 2021). FMCG products are functional products with thin margins but consistent market demand. Fisher (1997) suggested that the most

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appropriate supply network for functional products is an efficient supply chain. Cost efficiency is a hallmark of an efficient supply chain; hence all attempts should be made to cut costs (Muduliet et al., 2020, 2021). The key components of logistics costs are transportation and inventory; if these areas can be targeted and improved, logistics distribution performance can improve. In today's highly competitive global market, performance evaluation is critical for efficiently managing logistics operations. According to Wang et al. (2021), changes in outbound logistics can directly impact the FMCG delivery system for distributing finished goods and services. The timely availability of commodities and low inventory holding costs are ensured by well-managed distribution routes (Mishra and Mishra, 2021). The study investigates how digitalization might be used to alleviate these inefficiency issues. Integrating new technology into current processes can significantly improve customer service, lower costs, and streamline supply chains (Kenneth and Laudon, 2017). According to Sellitto et al. (2015), the development and expansion of digitalization significantly impact people's lives and work and bring new problems and opportunities for businesses in terms of operating modes and output in the marketplace. Digitalization and e-supply chains are seen as important drivers of flexibility, according to Ivanov et al. (2018), that can help in identifying the loopholes in the supply chain against which the organizations can take timely actions to avoid adverse consequences (Iddris, 2018; Tunio et al., 2021). This article aims to investigate the reasons and circumstances that lead to inefficiencies in logistics distribution, which raise costs and impair profitability for fast-moving consumer products companies. The two key components that directly impact logistics distribution competitiveness are warehousing and transportation. As a result, there is a pressing need to quantify transportation and warehousing inefficiencies. Using digital technological tools such as warehouse management systems (WMS) and transportation management systems (TMS), executives can capture the operating efficiency of key processes at the macro level, allowing them to take corrective action to improve existing operations.

2. Literature Review

The movement and storage of finished products from the manufacturing site to the consumer is referred to as physical distribution. Distribution can use direct or indirect means to put the systems into the customer's hands. While the assembling system might be quickly settled using existing advancements and in this manner is financially savvy, the dispersion cycle actually still needs to be convoluted and wasteful because of framework backwardness and regulatory deterrents, bringing about outstandingly high production network exchange costs (Lee and Chen, 2001). Rodrigues and Potter (2013) found significant varieties in vulnerability readiness and responsiveness among the dissemination networks concentrated on in the UK and South Africa. Njambi and Katuse (2013) did near

research to perceive how outsider operations (3PL) may further develop dissemination quality and efficiency to convey organizations an upper hand. Planned operations execution, estimated as far as coordinated factors expenses and quality, affects the monetary presentation of retail firms (Sanchez, 2022). Yang et al. (2021) took a gander at the connection between coordinated factors rehearses on the monetary execution, guaranteeing that incorporating firm IT capacities, interior and outside joint efforts, and inventory network reconciliation assists an organization with working all the more effectively monetarily (World Global Logistics Research Team, Michigan State University, 1995; European Logistics Association and A.T. Kearney, 2004). These investigations for the most part infer that operations greatness is straightforwardly connected with monetary greatness (D'Avanzo et al., 2003). Exceptional operations greatness is supposed to decidedly affect stock costs, diminishing expenses and expanding benefits (Christopher, 2016; Moons et al., 2019). According to a McKinsey study, India's logistics sector accounts for 14% of gross domestic product (GDP), well above 89% in the United States and Europe.

2.1. Relationship between transportation, warehouse optimization and logistic distribution performance

Transport optimization means superior transportation performance that leads to lower transportation spending (Hamilton and Maliphol, 2021), better service, enhanced sustainability (Rao, 2021), and increased asset utilization (Wu et al.; 2021). Because of the short shelf life of FMCG products (Bhakat et al.; 2021), most transportation is concentrated on road transportation, which also provides a lot of flexibility (Rossi et al.; 2021) and doorstep delivery. Transport management systems (TMS) positively and significantly influence the logistics distribution (Mahalia et al., 2021) of FMCG. The factors which are considered important and define transport performance are On-time delivery (Joghee et al. 2021; Privett and Gonsalvez, 2014; Zeng and Rossetti, 2003), enhanced visibility of in-transit vehicles (Zhang et al., 2011; Kumar et al., 2013, 2014, 2015; Pundir et al, 2019; Wanganoo, 2020), timely dock loading and unloading (Gupta and Jigeesh, 2019, Sanchez-Rodrigues et al., 2009), vehicle capacity utilization (Van de Klundert and Otten, 2011; Wang et al., 2020), and automatic vehicle scheduling (Zhang et al. 2022; Kukreja et al., 2020). Warehouse optimization (Islam 2021) refers to warehouse performance that increases customer experience and fulfillment by expanding the utilization of time, space, and assets in a stockroom through mechanization (Apolonio and Norona, 2021) and cautious plan. It alludes to the utilization of state of the art methods and innovation to improve inventory visibility, control, and management in order to improve service levels and customer satisfaction (Wang et al., 2021). Inventory tracking within the warehouse (Tejesh and Neeraja, 2018; Malindzakova and Zimon, 2019), proper documentation (Qazi,

2020; Yuen, 2017), faster putaway & picking (Tufano et al., 2022; Kumar and Kansara, 2018; Karim et al., 2020), effective order processing (Rudolph and Emmelmann, 2017; James and Inyang, 2022), and proper space utilization (Krishnadevarajan et al., 2015; Dixit et al., 2020) are all examples of improved warehouse performance. Transportation and warehouse operations account for a large portion of logistics costs; if these areas can be targeted and improved, logistics distribution performance may be improved. As a result, there is an urgent need to use digitalization to measure inefficiencies in transportation and inventories.

2.2. Relationship between digitalization and logistic distribution performance

According to Gartner (2018), Digitalization is "using digital technology to transform business models and create new revenue and value-creating opportunities" (Gebauer et al.; 2020). Digital transformation (Singh and Hess 2020; Kumar, 2020), is "the application of new technologies to achieve significant business benefits such as improving customer experience, process optimization, new business models" (Gong and Ribiere 2021). New technologies such as barcodes, RFID, sensors, warehouse management systems (WMS), transportation management systems (TMS), automated storage and retrieval systems (ASRS), robots, and the latest wearable computers have all been suggested as ways to improve logistics distribution performance. Digital technology has the potential to accelerate supply chain convergence (Kache and Seuring, 2017; Kumar, 2017; Memon et al., 2021), as well as the integration of data and information from multiple sources and locations to begin the production and distribution of products and services (Deepu and Ravi, 2021). The WMS improves warehouse efficiency and effectiveness while providing high levels of service reliability (Miralam, 2017, Mashhur and Attia, 2021). Fridah (2021), Mukolwe, and Wanyoike (2015) advocate a strategic approach to logistics management that incorporates current technologies and personnel training. Hao et al. (2020) recommended a structure for carrying out the "computerized warehousing framework (AWS)," while Latif and Shin (2020) introduced a framework that use incorporated blended reality procedures to diminish travel and pick time by helping perceivability. The Malmquist model showed that numerous digitization initiatives have a significant long-term impact on transportation effectiveness (Loske and Klumpp 2022). Hu et al. (2019) create an internet-based approach for finding hubs and routing loads at a capacity level. Resat and Turkay (2019) used a mixed-integer linear optimization model to study the Turkish transportation business. Elnaz Irannez had proposed blockchain as a solution for fragmented freight transportation that suffers from a lack of confidence and openness. The elements of digitalization explored for this study under transportation are vehicle tracking systems (VTS) (Lee et al., 2014, Tian et al., 2018), transport management systems (TMS) and vehicle capacity utilization tools in the context of fast-moving

consumer products distribution. Similarly, Warehouse management systems (WMS), Enterprise resource planning (ERP) and Barcodes have been considered for Warehousing.

Various scholars have aimed to examine the role of digitalization in various sectors, but no assessment of the influence of digitalization on the physical distribution of fast-moving consumer goods has been made to the best of authors' knowledge. This research aims to close that gap. This research will look for inefficiencies in physical distribution and how the performance of the primary components of physical distribution (warehousing and transportation) might be enhanced by digitalization. This research is designed to identify the factors which lead to inefficiency in the physical distribution of FMCG goods and to understand the role of digitalization in transportation and warehousing in improving the logistics distribution performance.

3. Conceptual research model and hypotheses

In view of the writing audit, the estimation model and speculations for the exogenous (free) factors, interceding variable, and endogenous (subordinate) factors were created to depict the interlinkages between the influencing factor and their immediate and aberrant effect on LDPP, as shown in Figure 2. Two exogenous latent constructs, Transport performance (TPP) and Warehouse performance (WPP), as well as two mediating variables, Transport digitalization (TDGT) and Warehouse digitalization (WDGT), and one endogenous latent construct, Logistics Distribution Performance (LDP), were used in this study (LDPP).

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

We formulate the following hypotheses:

- H1: Transportation optimization (TPP) has a positive impact on logistics distribution performance (LDPP).
- H1a: Transport optimization (TPP) has a positive impact on transport digitalization (TDGT).
- H1b: Transport digitalization (TDGT) has a positive impact on logistics distribution performance (LDPP).
- H2: Warehouse optimization (WPP) has a positive impact on logistics distribution performance (LDPP).
- H2a: Warehouse optimization (WPP) has a positive impact on warehouse digitalization (WDGT).
- H2b: Warehouse digitalization (WDGT) has a positive impact on logistics distribution performance (LDPP)

4. Methodology

This study tries to identify and examine the barriers to the effective distribution of fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) and the role digitalization can play in overcoming these barriers to make the process efficient as these products are characterized by lower margins. For investigation, the survey data was collected from various employees engaged in the distribution, i.e., warehouse management, customer service, transport management, demand and supply planning and other areas of the FMCG sector.

4.1. Data collection

As part of a quantitative research technique, the information was gathered through self-managed surveys with shut finished questions. Respondents were reached by means of interior mail frameworks at every one of the taking part organizations. The review was intentional, and there was no money related motivating force. Thus, the accumulated information was exposed to SEM examination involving AMOS 27 to guarantee that the recommended speculative *endlessly model fit were precise*.

4.2. Sampling

More than 500 questionnaires were circulated, and 300 responses were received, with 44 surveys being removed owing to missing information. In total, 256 questionnaires were analyzed. The response rate is substantially greater, and the sampled population is more accurately represented. The survey data was automatically transmitted to an excel sheet, which was then manually entered into an SPSS database. The data was verified and authenticated in accordance with industry standards (e.g., Missing value prototype, Range, distribution).

4.3. The instrument

Each of the study's six hypotheses is examined in one of the survey's four components. The first component collects respondents' personal and demographic information, such as name, work experience, gender, age, education, and so on. The second segment contains five transportation-related things (TPP). The third section contains information on warehouse performance (WPP). The role of digitalization (DGT) in increasing transportation and warehousing performance is explored in the fourth section. The sixth section covers logistics distribution performance (LDPP). Segments 2-5 were surveyed on a five-point Likert scale, with 1 showing solid conflict and 5 demonstrating solid understanding. After conducting a thorough literature analysis on the subject, the items for the study concepts were created. To ensure the items' content legitimacy, expert opinion was sought. On the substance of these items, two industry professionals and two academic specialists were contacted for their input. Items were finally incorporated to reflect respective study themes after appropriate revisions were made as indicated by experts. As a measure of study concept reliability, Cronbach's alpha was examined, and the scores for each scale were found to be above the stipulated threshold values, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Reliability and Standard factor loading of the items

Construct	Items	Standardized Weights	CR	Cronbach Alpha
Transport Performance	TP1	0.807	0.943	0.941
	TP2	0.89		
	TP3	0.92		
	TP4	0.936		
	TP5	0.82		
Warehouse Performance	WP1	0.626	0.908	0.907
	WP2	0.847		
	WP3	0.77		
	WP4	0.758		
	WP5	0.847		
	WP6	0.869		
Digitalization	TDGT1	0.698	0.899	0.894
	TDGT2	0.849		
	TDGT3	0.894		
	WDGT1	0.763		
	WDGT2	0.807		
	WDGT3	0.61		
Logistics Distribution Performance	LDP1	0.76	0.928	0.927
	LDP2	0.877		
	LDP3	0.85		
	LDP4	0.879		
	LDP5	0.801		
	LDP6	0.789		

In terms of validity, an AMOS measurement model was used, and the results showed that all study scales had both discriminant and convergent validity.

Table 2: Convergent and discriminant Validity

Construct	Items	AVE	ASV	P
Transport Performance	TP1	0.767	0.230	***
	TP2			***
	TP3			***
	TP4			***
	TP5			
Warehouse Performance	WP1	0.624	0.1686	***
	WP2			***
	WP3			***
	WP4			***
	WP5			***
	WP6			
Digitalization	TDGT1	0.602	0.198	***
	TDGT2			***
	TDGT3			***
	WDGT1			***
	WDGT2			***
	WDGT3			
Logistics Distribution Performance	LDP1	0.684	0.239	***
	LDP2			***
	LDP3			***
	LDP4			***
	LDP5			***
	LDP6			
Note : * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$				

5. Data analysis and results

5.1. Sample characteristics

Table 3 shows the segment attributes of the respondents. Males represented 67% of the 256 respondents, while females represented 33%. With 53% in the long term age bunch and 47 percent in the long term age bunch working all day, most of the members were utilized full-time. Most of individuals who answered worked in the quick customer merchandise industry and knew about the variables that impact planned operations circulation execution.

Table 3: Sample Profile (Demographic)

Variable	Categories	Response %
Gender	Male	67
	Female	33
Age Group	20-40	53
	41-60	47
Experience	0-10 yrs	55
	11-15 yrs	30
	15+ yrs	15

Common method bias: There are times when common method bias should be a major issue; for example, it is usually accepted that common method bias pumps up relationships between variables. Since the review depended on self-revealed information, there is plausible of a typical technique inclination (Podsakoff et al., 2003). Subsequently, Harman's strategy was utilized to dispose of these predispositions to decrease the issue. All free and subordinate factors were additionally exposed to exploratory element examination (EFA) using head part investigation. On the off chance that a solitary part makes sense of a lopsidedly huge measure of the fluctuation, this is an indication of Common Method Bias (CMB). However, the development of a single component accounted for approximately 16 percent of the variance in our analysis, indicating that CMB is not a severe threat to our findings.

Structural equation modeling (SEM): Structural equation modeling (SEM) is a multivariate strategy that investigates a bunch of ward connections in a speculated model simultaneously. It has two instruments: one for estimation and the other for underlying examination, and it incorporates different relapse with corroborative element investigation (CFA). An estimation model, as indicated by Doloi et al. (2011), is fundamentally worried about the legitimacy and dependability of inactive factors and discernible factors, as well as their relationship. The underlying model spotlights on the way power and connection between the inactive factors.

The measurement model: The estimation model is tried, AMOS 27 is utilized to play out a corroborative element investigation (CFA). Prior to inspecting at the underlying model's interrelationships, it's basic to take a gander at the estimation model's legitimacy and unwavering quality (Fornell and Lacker, 1981; Ifinedo, 2006).

Figure 3 depicts the final measurement model, which includes four constructs: TPP, WPP, DGT, and LDPP, where Transport performance is represented by five items and the rest are represented by six items, for a total of 23 measured indicator variables. The estimating model's boundaries were surveyed for unwavering quality, united legitimacy, and

discriminant legitimacy (see Table 1). Interior consistency is examined to decide dependability, which demonstrates that the unwavering quality of everything in the survey was intended to quantify a similar trait. Cronbach's alpha is utilized to evaluate the interior consistency of each develop (TPP, WPP, TDGT, WDG, and LDPP) by working out the pairwise relationship between things, that reach from 0 to 1.

Figure 2: Conceptual Model

Cronbach's alpha is considered trustworthy somewhere in the range of 0.6 and 0.7, and it is considered to have a serious level of dependability in the event that it is bigger than 0.7. (Sekaran, 2003). Table 1 shows that the level of dependability for each develop is over 0.7 and near 0.9. The outcomes show that each build's inner consistency is great. Thus, these measurements are suitable and can be utilized for primary condition demonstrating (SEM) investigation. Composite unwavering quality is utilized to survey the trustworthiness of a

build in an estimation model (CR). CR, a more noticeable strategy to assess largely dependability, is utilized to decide the develop's consistency (Hair et al., 2010). The composite reliability (CR) in the measurement model, as indicated in Table 1, is more than 0.7. As a result, all constructions are extremely dependable in the measurement model.

Validity requires studying the right thing, just as reliability refers to studying the right way (Collis and Hussey 2013; Saunders et al. 2009). Because the empirical data is primarily gathered from various executives and managers, there is a possibility of subjectivity, which could reduce the study's validity. To address this both convergent and discriminant validity was determined. The degree to which factors of a specific build have a significant extent of variety is alluded to as focalized legitimacy (Hair et al., 2010). Joined legitimacy is resolved utilizing standard relapse loads. Standard component stacking (standard relapse weight) assessments show that the pointer factors fundamentally address the secret factors. The variable stacking standard ought to never be under 0.50 (Hair et al., 2010). Table 1 shows that the noticed variable's standard component stacking ranges somewhere in the range of 0.75 and 0.95. Concurrent legitimacy ought to be affirmed whether the deliberate factors are adequate and stick to the idle variable or develop.

How much a develop contrasts from different builds is estimated utilizing discriminant legitimacy (Hair et al., 2010). The discriminant legitimacy can be evaluated utilizing one of two different ways. In the first place, there ought not be areas of strength for a between evaluations of hypothetically particular develops (Trochim et al., 2006). Second, the worth of square root AVE ought to be more noteworthy than the connection between's develops, on the grounds that typical extricated differences (AVE) of explicit builds are consistently more prominent than normal shared changes (ASV) between builds. As found in Table 1, the AVE of the particular designs surpasses the ASV.

The model fit was evaluated utilizing the similar fit file (CFI), integrity of fit record (GFI), normed fit file (NFI), Tucker Lewis list (TLI), and root mean square of blunder estimate (RMSEA) (Hair et al., 2010). The upsides of χ^2/df ought to be under 3, CFI, GFI, NFI, and TLI ought to all be near or more prominent than 0.9, and the root mean square blunder estimation (RMSEA) ought to continuously be under 0.08 to lay out an OK fit with information (Gefen and Straub, 2000). The table beneath sums up the integrity-of-fit files for the model fit. Table 3 shows that the estimation model recommends a solid match, consequently we might utilize SEM to test the underlying model.

Table 4: Goodness-of-fit indices (summary for Measurement Model)

Model fit index	χ^2/df	CFI	GFI	NFI	TLI	RMSEA
Model fit index	2.994	0.935	0.863	0.906	0.927	0.072

Whereas, CFI indicates comparative fit index; GFI indicates goodness of fit index; NFI indicates normed fit index; TLI indicates Tucker Lewis index; RMSEA indicates root mean square error approximation

Structural model: SEM was used to assess the structural model in order to examine the hypothesized conceptual research model. The goodness-of-fit for the model, which is judged to be moderately satisfactory, is shown in Table 4. As a result, we can move forward with our investigation of the hypotheses described in our model.

Table 5: Goodness-of-fit indices summary for Structural Model

Model fit index	χ^2 /df	CFI	GFI	NFI	TLI	RMSEA
Model fit index	3.587	0.943	0.883	0.922	0.933	0.082

The table shows the structural model's properties (standardized path coefficients (β), standard error, critical ratio, and hypotheses outcome.

Table 6: Summary of testing

Hypothesis		Structural Relationship	St. Est (β)	Unst.Est (β)	P	Result
H1	Total Effect	TPP---LDPP	0.37	0.41	***	supported
	Direct Effect	TPP---LDPP	0.26	0.3	***	
H2	Total Effect	WPP---LDPP	0.45	0.35	***	supported
	Direct Effect	WPP---LDPP	0.41	0.33	***	
H1a		TPP---TDGT	0.53	0.55	***	supported
H1b		TDGT--LDPP	0.06	0.03	***	supported
H2a		WPP--WDGT	0.33	0.21	***	supported
H2b		WDGT--LDPP	0.24	0.2	***	supported

Mediation analysis: The way hypothesis expected three underlying ways, one from TPP-LDPP (without Mediating factors), Second from WPP- LDPP. The huge intercession is upheld through TPP- TDGT- LDPP; notwithstanding, the other meditational way, for example WPP- WDG- LDPP is viewed as irrelevant as displayed in Table 7.

Table 7: Mediation Analysis

Mediating Effect	In the relationship of	Sobel Test	P	Result
TDGT	TPP----LDPP	0.4196	***	Supported
WDGT	WPP----LDPP	0.0817	***	Supported

Test of the total effect: The TPP — LDPP is the primary underlying course (without interceding factors). The general still up in the air to be genuinely critical ($\beta = 0.37$, $p < 0.001$). Similarly, WPP — LDPP (without intervening factors). The whole not entirely set in stone to be measurably huge ($\beta = 0.45$, $p < 0.001$).

Test of direct effect: Presently, the model was run with interceding variable, the normalized way coefficient (β) from TPP- LDPP was decreased by a non-insignificant sum ($\beta = 0.37-0.26$), and correspondingly WPP- LDPP was diminished by ($\beta = 0.45-0.41$), however still critical; hence, the incomplete intervention was upheld (Baron and Kenny, 1986). Speculation H1 suggested that TPP is emphatically influencing the LDPP and WPP is decidedly LDPP. Consequently, the aftereffect of the primary condition model offered help for H1 and H2 speculations.

Test of indirect effect: The way by means of (TPP- TDGT- LDPP) showed measurably critical aberrant consequences for LDPP through digitalisation ($z = 4.7, p < 0.001$). Theory H2a hypothesized a positive connection between Transport execution (TPP) and Logistics dispersion execution (LDPP). The path coefficient between TPP and LDPP ($\beta = 0.77, p < 0.001$) was significant, supporting Hypotheses H2a. Further hypothesis H2b which proposed a positive relationship between WPP and, LDPP was also supported ($\beta = 0.43, p < 0.001$), so warehouse performance do lead to Logistics distribution performance. In turn, in the path via (TPP-TDGT-LDPP).

Sobel test: While the intervening variable is incorporated to the situation, specialists accept that it isn't sufficient to report whether the size of the connection between the indicator and the result variable becomes halfway or full intercession (Frazier et al., 2004). Accordingly, we utilize the Sobel (1982) test to affirm the interceding variable's importance. This test utilizes both the indicator arbitrator variable way (1) and the mediator result variable way (2) or stomach muscle. The interceding variable not entirely set in stone by partitioning the interceding variable evaluations by their standard mistake and contrasting the subsequent worth with a standard typical dispersion (Sobel, 1982; Gunasekaran et al., 2017). The circuitous impact (Sab) has a standard blunder of.

$$s_{ab} = \sqrt{b^2 s_a^2 + a^2 s_b^2 + s_a^2 s_b^2} \tag{1}$$

where a denotes unstandardised relapse coefficient of the way a ; b unstandardised relapse coefficient of way b ; S_a standard mistake of a and S_b standard blunder of b .

To summarise, the findings show that initiatives aimed at improving warehouse and transportation digitalization can boost logistics distribution performance. According to the findings, the majority of respondents agree that transportation optimization (TPP) and warehouse optimization (WPP) elements have a positive influence on logistics distribution (LDPP), and their opinions are consistent across job types, gender, and age. These findings are interesting given that firms consider that warehouse and transportation digitization are required to improve the logistics distribution performance of fast-moving consumer goods. TPP, WPP, and LDPP were used to create structural models, with LDPP as the dependent

variable and TPP and WPP as the independent variables. Transport digitalization (TDGT) and Warehouse digitalization (WDGT) were also used as mediating variables. Unidimensionality, reliability, discriminant validity, and convergent validity were all satisfied for all constructs. As a result, they are statistically valid.

The study examines the direct and indirect links between transportation optimization (TPP), warehouse optimization (WPP), digitization (DGT), and logistics distribution performance (LDPP). We examine the relationship in the model between Warehouse optimization (WPP) and Logistics distribution performance (LDPP) in one structure and transportation optimization and Logistics distribution performance (LDPP) in the other. Also, we proposed the mediating mechanism of warehouse digitalization (WDGT) and transport digitalization (TDGT). The output of the analysis supports the research hypotheses. As a result, we have filled a hole in the existing literature by establishing a link between digitization and logistics distribution performance. Furthermore, we discovered that digitization partially mediates the impact of transportation and warehouse effectiveness on logistics distribution performance.

The current study empirically evaluates and demonstrates that warehouse and transportation efficiency plays a significant influence in improving logistics distribution performance. The findings show that embracing digitalization can help FMCG companies enhance their distribution effectiveness. As a result of its importance in distribution performance, organizations that use digital solutions in transportation and warehousing may create higher revenues by making the processes more efficient.

Our findings suggest that management acts as a facilitator when they are convinced of the importance of digitization in boosting distribution performance. To achieve better results, organizations need active employee participation and involvement. Management must motivate employees by giving training and imparting skills to promote awareness as many people engaged in this sector do not have sound knowledge regarding the latest technologies in the distribution domain. Moldabekova (2021) attempted to draw a link between digital technologies and EU countries' logistical performance. (Toyli et al., 2008) explored the impact of better logistics on financial performance, which in turn affects organizational performance. The current study addresses a gap in previous research by looking at how warehouse and transportation optimization increases logistics distribution performance through digitalization in these domains.

6. Implications Conclusion

The performance of logistics distribution in the fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) sector is influenced by numerous warehousing and transportation activities. Because most shipping and warehousing services are outsourced to third-party logistics service

providers, it is critical to have seamless coordination in all of these activities. Organizations are being compelled to evaluate how they may take advantage of digitalization to better manage their supply chain activities due to innovative technical advancements, increased global competitiveness, and fast-changing client needs. The inherent digital technologies improve responsiveness, through cross-organizational business processes collaborations, particularly in the case of demand variations, as well as flexibility in the face of constrained capacity.

In India, the FMCG sector is an emerging and rapidly increasing business sector that has an impact on everyone's life, either directly or indirectly. According to the literature assessment, there are several inefficiencies across the supply chain. Physical distribution suffers the most because it is typically outsourced and handled by third-party logistics (3PL) partners, over whom the company has limited control. According to the literature, several research have been conducted to highlight supply chain inefficiencies, however, there is scarcely any study accessible in India that discusses the impact of digitization in enhancing the physical distribution of fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG). This research gap is addressed in this study. The study reveals poor visibility of in-transit vehicles, loading-unloading delays at docks, manual scheduling of vehicles, inventory tracking within warehouses, poor documentation, slower putaways/picking, picking inaccuracies, slow order processing, etc. are the main factors identified which are leading to inefficiencies in the physical distribution. These factors can be addressed with digital tools like ERP, EDI, TMS, etc. which will improve the efficiency of physical distribution. The importance of digital information exchange in improving physical distribution is highlighted in this research. The findings also offer managerial recommendations for how companies might use digital data to streamline the distribution process. Furthermore, the study can only provide indications due to the qualitative character of the results; quantitative confirmatory studies would further strengthen the conclusions.

The focus of this research is on the physical distribution of fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) in Northern India. Specific elements such as infrastructure, level of technology advancement, resource availability, and employee expertise may change as geography and products change. Only the most critical variable under each identified component for inefficiencies in the physical distribution of fast-moving consumer items is measured in this study (FMCG).

The research undertaken has opened up new research avenues for the future. Because the study's measures are limited to only the most critical variable under each identified factor for inefficiency, subsequent studies may look at measures for additional factors. A comparable analysis might also be conducted in other geographical regions or compared to the supply chains of developed countries. A comparable analysis might be conducted for

the supply chain of adjacent industries such as consumer durables, pharmaceutical cold chains, and food and beverage industries.

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